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Organizational citizenship behavior from the pedagogical perspective

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to elucidate certain results of an analysis of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) and its components from a pedagogical perspective. Based on teachers' interviews, we find a strong interconnection between teachers' OCB components. The main findings of our research can serve as a relevant framework for practical

interventions on how to improve teachers' activity. In practice, OCB analysis should be connected with various personal, organizational, demographic, and cognitive variables and environmental variables.

Keywords: organizational citizenship behaviour; analysis, relationship, teachers.

Rezumat: Articolul elucidează unele rezultate ale studiului dedicat analizei comportamentului civic organizațional (CCO) și componentelor sale din perspectivă pedagogică. Pe baza interviurilor cu profesorii, constatăm o interconexiune puternică între componentele CCO ale profesorilor. Principalele constatări ale cercetării pot servi drept cadru relevant pentru intervenții practice de îmbunătățire a activității profesorilor. În plan practic, analiza CCO ar trebui conectată cu diverse variabile personale, organizaționale, demografice, cognitive și variabile de mediu.

Cuvinte-cheie: comportament civic organizațional, analiză, relaționare, profesori.

At the current stage, when the world community is marked by such processes as the globalization of the economy and the informatization of society, they have led to the emergence of new approaches to human behavior and the methodology of organizing human activity.

The literature in the field of adult pedagogy, work, and organizational psychology expands the meaning given to the notion of behavior by traditional behaviorism. Behavior is no longer seen as just a stimulus-response reaction, but as a manifestation of the psycho-social life of the individual in an organizational context.

One of the main concepts in organizational behavior literature is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Of the various terminology used in research literature to describe actions that go beyond the formal, obligatory aspects of one's job, the term *organizational citizenship behavior* has won the most scholarly attention. It refers to professional activities performed without direct compensation, which are perceived as significant to the organization's efficiency and function [2; 5].

The research field of OCB is continuously changing. The foundations of organizational behavior were laid by work sociology, managerial theory, organizational theory etc. The research carried out in the field of organizational behavior contributed to finding the means of efficiency of the production activity. More recently, the topic was extended to the educational field.

What is OCB and its components? *Organizational citizenship behavior* is a term coined by Dennis W.

Organ, who is considered to have 'fathered' the theory in the late 1970s-early 1980s. The term has crystallized over the years and is now the topic of a growing number of studies. The term *organizational citizenship behavior* refers to a longstanding phenomenon of voluntary behavior and mutual aid without request for official remuneration.

At the same time, OCB is defined as a multidimensional concept [1] "... which includes all of the individual's positive behaviors in the organization such as traditional role behaviors, behaviors that go beyond the job description, and political behaviors such as full participation in the organization". These are not officially included in the job description, but are nevertheless desired by the organization and perceived as valuable to individuals (other employees, for instance) and the organization as a whole [6].

Over the years, several ways of conceptualizing OCB have emerged (cf. Bateman & Organ, 1983; Organ, 1988, 1990; Smith et al., 1983; Van Dyne, Graham and Dienesch, 1994; Williams & Anderson, 1991)[Apud 7]. However, two conceptualizations remain the most popular: those developed by Organ [3; 4] and Williams and Anderson [8].

Originally, Organ proposed a five-factor OCB model consisting of altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue, and sportsmanship. However, he subsequently expanded this model to include two other dimensions (peacekeeping and cheerleading) [7].

The second major conceptualization of OCB is the one proposed by Williams and Anderson [8]. More specifically, they call behaviors aimed at benefiting other individuals *OCBI*, while behaviors aimed at benefiting the organization are called *OCBO*. In addition, the authors' categorization scheme incorporates most other OCB-related constructs.

Podsakoff et al. identified nearly 30 different forms of behavior and classified them into seven common dimensions. Organ's dimensions of altruism, courtesy, peacekeeping, and cheerleading were combined into a "helping" behavior construct [6].

Based on specialized literature, we explored several components to analyze OCB in relation with teachers' behaviors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. *Teacher's OCB components*

- The first component, **helping behavior**, earned the most scholarly attention. This component means that teachers help students with class materials, acquire expertise in new areas that contribute to their work, volunteer for school committees, help absent colleagues by assigning learning tasks to their classes, work collaboratively with others etc.
- The second component, **sportsmanship**, targets teachers who show a "sportsmanlike" spirit, usually avoid losing their working hours with various complaints, show self-sacrifice for the benefit of the group and the institution, and tend to have a positive attitude towards the others.
- The third component is **organizational loyalty**, and it refers to the promotion of the institution as a whole, both by protecting its reputation from external threats and by promoting its image in society.

- The fourth component, **organizational compliance**, refers to teachers' internalization of the organization's rules and regulations, even when they are not subject to external oversight. This component aligns with high-level organizational culture, including behaviors such as punctuality, disciplinarity, avoiding extra breaks etc.
- The fifth component, **personal initiative**, is also considered OCB, given that teachers' organizational initiative goes beyond the daily requirements listed in their job description. Moreover, this behavior includes situations when a teacher proposes possible improvements to the didactic process/curriculum, volunteers for new initiatives, or accepts forced changes.
- The sixth component, **civic virtue**, manifests itself through the teacher's attendance of staff meetings and reporting of potential risks the organization may face in the future. This behavior aims at the teachers' commitment to the institution as a whole, but also at their willingness to accept personal responsibility for its success.
- The final component, **personal development**, refers to the voluntary participation of teachers in professional development programs, participation in didactic-scientific activities, professional internships etc. In this sense, the important thing is personal commitment without imposing on the administration.

In the context of what has been elucidated above, based on interviews with teachers, we find that the helping behaviors were presented as an excellent relationship between "old" teachers (with more experience) and "new" ones (with less experience), showing through support, encouragement, and collaboration. The respondents reported emotional support for "new" teachers, being listened to on workplace issues, initiated in recognizing school culture and many teaching problems. The experienced teachers offered all this without any monetary reward or without being obliged to do so by the regulations of the Ministry of Education in Israel.

At the same time, we would note that such a phenomenon is predominant mainly in primary schools, while in secondary schools the tendency to absorb a new teacher is better shaped.

The most basic definition involves the transfer of pedagogical knowledge and an effective classroom management. In accordance with this, the interviewees and assessing learners attributed pedagogical knowledge transfer, assessment, measurement of learner's achievements, social education, and preparation rate to a teacher's official role, i.e. these are tasks that the teacher is committed to make *ex officio*. According to most of the interviewees in this study, the teacher

is committed to "cover the material" according to the curriculum, to prepare the students for exams, to make sure that the students really understand the material, to prepare lessons, to give assignments, to assess the achievements of learners, to track their progress, and to educate the students about democratic values and moral behavior. These tasks included, in one form or another, in the circular Director General (1994), which defined the roles of teachers and their mission.

In contrast, and somewhat surprisingly, initiating changes and innovation and implementing them, diversifying teaching methods and curricula, offering individualized instruction and in-depth assessment, and making a comprehensive analysis of students' achievements were seen by respondents as manifestations of non-mandatory civil behavior in school teachers. Despite a number of educational reforms over the years, which emphasized the importance of teacher initiatives, integrated teaching methods, and various assessment tools, the respondents in this study did not perceive these aspects of a teacher's role as part of the tasks required of the teacher, but on the contrary, such discretionary, creative, and innovative elements of teaching were seen as components of civil behavior in school teachers.

Teachers indicated that they are rewarded for transmitting to the students a higher volume of knowledge or for developing new programs, such as programs of excellence in the subject of space, mathematics, or sciences. Civil behavior was reflected in the development of textbooks, workbooks, brochures exercises and the like for the children of their class. After all, they could have settled for magazines purchased by students and textbooks approved by the Ministry of Education.

Another expression of OCB is to significantly adjust the teaching to the needs and capabilities of specific, a teaching method described in literature as contributing to the effectiveness of teaching in schools where learning is not organized in groups. Especially in high schools, many teachers would teach different content for different students, employing a variety of teaching methods according to the students' level, even if this instruction consumes time and effort and is not rewarded in itself. Such activities were perceived by the majority of the study participants as OCB. At the same time, a good number of respondents, especially in the core system, believed that such a performance is an integral part of the official job description for a teacher.

In conclusion: Behavior in schools is different from that found in non-educational settings. Schools, compared to non-educational organizations, are service institutions made up of teachers, professional people

who, in general, assume responsibilities dedicated to providing the best possible services to their clients – the children. In this respect, the influence of the nature of work on the teacher's OCB may be different from that in other organizations.

Based on literature review and teachers' interviews, we found some differences between OCB perception in general schools and high schools. Our main findings present an eloquent framework for structuring a number of practical interventions. We believe that OCB analysis should be connected with various personal, organizational, demographic, and cognitive variables and environmental variables.

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